

“Monitoring and Evaluation Report”

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5.12.2024	<i>draft based on feedback from project partners</i>	V1.2
16.12.2024	<i>draft based on feedback from Steering Committee</i>	V1.3
20.12.2024	<i>final version submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V2.0
22.07.2025	<i>initial draft (M36) by partners responsible</i>	V2.1
29.07.2025	<i>draft based on feedback from project partners</i>	V2.2
13.08.2025	<i>draft based on feedback from Steering Committee</i>	V2.3
19.08.2025	<i>final version submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V3.0
19.09.2025	<i>final version based on comments from final review meeting</i>	V4.0

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components were successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. INDUSAC created a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including companies, students and researchers. The INDUSAC achieved a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that leveraged the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

The deliverable D3.5 Monitoring and Evaluation report includes a timeline of activities of the INDUSAC Evaluation Board from the publication of the call for students and researchers to the deadline for submission of the solutions developed by INDUSAC co-creation teams of students and researchers. It also provides statistics on the number of published companies' challenges, motivation letters submitted by co-creation teams, initiated co-creation projects, and completed co-creation projects. Additionally, the report presents a record of approved solutions of co-creation teams. Furthermore, the analysis of the survey results offers valuable feedback from students and researchers on their skills before and after their co-creation projects. Similarly, feedback from companies on their satisfaction with the INDUSAC process and platform, the co-creation team's work, the provided solution, and additional comments are included. The insights gained from analysing the survey results have been used to improve the methodology and platform, and to provide data for verifying the achievement of Objectives 5 and 7 of the INDUSAC project. The parts of Objective 5 and Objective 7 relevant to this Deliverable are marked in bold below. The outcomes from all cut-offs (11.02.2024, 18.06.2024, 30.09.2024, 30.10.2024, 30.11.2024, 30.01.2025, 28.02.2025, 31.03.2025, and 15.04.2025) regarding the bold parts of the Objectives can be confirmed and are explained in the following chapters.

“Objective 5: To extract from the pilot activity all the necessary data and information and to analyse and process it to demonstrate the effectiveness of the INDUSAC mechanism in achieving the outcomes aimed for by it and the long-term sustainability of offering it to the EU academic and business community, as verified using the following measurements:

- Demonstration of the feasibility of running the IAC mechanism with less than €3,000 per co-creation team
- **“At least 70 % of students and researchers participating reporting at least one core professional transversal and entrepreneurial skill having been significantly developed by participating in the piloting of the INDUSAC IAC mechanism.”** This can be confirmed for all periods of the INDUSAC project's call for students and researchers since over 87 % of participating students and researchers report that their skills in a “Negotiation and Conflict management”, “Experience in working with companies and international teams skills”, as well as “Creativity”, “Critical Thinking”, “Time Management”, and “Leadership” have been significantly developed by participating in the piloting of the INDUSAC IAC mechanism.
- **“At least 70 % of SMEs reporting that the solution(s) delivered by the co-creation quick intervention were highly relevant to their company and contributed to overcoming the challenge that was identified by them (and which was accepted by the programme as being suitable).”** This can be confirmed for all periods of the INDUSAC project's call for

students and researchers since the majority of companies (77 % in the 1st period, 87 % in the 2nd period and 92 % in the 3rd period) report the overall satisfaction with the solutions.

- **“At least 80 % of students and SME staff stating that it is likely or highly likely they would recommend participation in such a programme to their peers.”** This has been **confirmed** for all periods of the INDUSAC project's call for students and researchers: Most students (90 % in the 1st period, 91 % in the 2nd period and 94 % in the 3rd period) **stated that they are likely or highly likely to recommend participation** in the programme to their peers

“Objective 7. To accelerate university students' exposure to real business environments and to promote the upskilling of university students' transversal and entrepreneurial skills (communication, negotiation, results oriented, responsibility, creativity, planning skills, analytical thinking, among others).”

- **“To provide a methodological framework to accelerate the upskilling of students in the entrepreneurial and transversal skills abovementioned, critical for their future employability.”** This can be **confirmed** for all periods of the INDUSAC project's call for students and researchers since **over 87 % of students and researchers observed upskilling in the entrepreneurial and transversal skills abovementioned, critical for their future employability.**

- **“To improve this set of skills (transversal and entrepreneurial skills (communication, negotiation, results oriented, responsibility, creativity, planning skills, analytical thinking, among others) in students and researchers in at least 30 % compared to before the beginning of the project, allowing them to rapidly expand their skillset in a short period of time and to find themselves more prepared for the business environment.”** This can be **confirmed** for all periods of the INDUSAC project's call for students and researchers since **90 % out of 531 students and researchers** who filled out the questionnaire (taking into account that a given individual filled the questionnaire for each team separately) **have reported improvements of skills.**

- **“At least 1000 students and researchers will be supported in real business environments throughout project lifetime.”** This can be partially confirmed, as **581** cases of students and researchers have been **supported in real business environments throughout project lifetime.**

LIST OF ACRONYMS

INDUSAC	Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations
JSI	Jožef Stefan Institute, member of the INDUSAC consortium, project coordinator
EB	Evaluation Board
FSTP	Financial Support for Third Parties
PCA	Predefined Collaborative Approach
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
D	Deliverable
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
M	Month
IAC	Industry Academia Collaboration
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats

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I. TIMELINE OF THE CALL FOR STUDENTS AND RESEARCHERS (FROM CALL OPENING UP TO THE CUT-OFF DATE)

The timeline for the first cut-off date (11.02.2024; 23:59 CET) of the INDUSAC project call for students and researchers was as follows:

- Publication of the call for students and researchers November 2023
- The deadline for submitting a Motivation Letter by teams of students and researchers was 11.02.2024.
- From the submission deadline until 10.03.2024, the companies selected the teams to work on the challenges. For rejected Motivation Letters, companies used pre-defined justifications.
- Until 22.03.2024, students were required to sign the FSTP declaration, marking the commencement of the co-creation project.
- All co-creation teams were expected to submit final reports, including a summary, deliverables as defined in PCAs, an upskilling questionnaire, and a testimonial, by 22.05.2024.
- Companies reviewed the solution for a challenge and deliverables submitted by the co-creation teams until 29.05.2024.
- On 12.06.2024, the Evaluation Board reviewed rejected solutions and confirmed the list of students to be funded.

The timeline for the second cut-off date (18.06.2024, 23:59 CET) of the INDUSAC project call for students and researchers was as follows:

- Until 25.06.2024 INDUSAC Challenge managers reviewed the received Motivation Letters and reject those not in English or Latin alphabet.
- Until 09.07.2024, companies made final selections. For rejected Motivation Letters, companies use pre-defined justifications.
- Until 23.07.2024, students signed the FSTP declaration, at which time the co-creation project begins.
- 30.07.-30.08.2024, the Mentoring Committee carried out in-depth monitoring of co-creation projects
- Until 16.09.2024 all co-creation teams submitted final reports (summary, deliverables as defined in PCAs, upskilling questionnaire, testimonial).
- Until 23.09.2024, companies reviewed the Summary and Deliverables.
- Until 30.09.2024, the Evaluation Board confirmed the list of students from the co-creation teams to be funded.
- Until 30.10.2024, all students from the list received funding (provided that the administrative procedure from the students' side has been finalised).

After the second cut-off, there were additional seven cut-offs that followed the same timeline: 30.09.2024, 30.10.2024, 30.11.2024, 30.01.2025, 28.02.2025, 31.03.2025, and 15.04.2025.

II. NUMBER OF PUBLISHED CHALLENGES, NUMBER OF SUBMITTED MOTIVATION LETTERS, NUMBER OF APPROVED MOTIVATION LETTERS, NUMBER OF FINISHED CO-CREATION PROJECTS

During the first period (11.02.2024-29.05.2024) of the INDUSAC's call for companies and call for students and researchers with one cut-off date, on 11.02.2024, the following results were achieved:

- Number of published Challenges by companies: 71
- Number of submitted Motivation Letters by teams of students and researchers: 21
- Number of approved Motivation Letters of teams of students and researchers: 16
- Number of finished co-creation projects: 13

During the second period (30.05.2024- 10.10.2024) of the INDUSAC's call for companies and call for students and researchers with one cut-off date, on 18.06.2024, the following results were achieved:

- Number of published Challenges by companies: 131 **(+60)**
- Number of submitted Motivation Letters by teams of students and researchers: 64 **(+43)**
- Number of approved Motivation Letters of teams of students and researchers: 37 **(+21)**
- Number of finished co-creation projects: 25 **(+12)**

During the third period (11.10.2024-10.07.2025) of the INDUSAC's call for companies and call for students and researchers with seven cut-off dates, last on 15.04.2025, the following results were achieved:

- Number of published Challenges by companies: 251 **(+120)**
- Number of submitted Motivation Letters by teams of students and researchers: 232 **(+168)**
- Number of approved Motivation Letters of teams of students and researchers: 164 **(+127)**
- Number of finished co-creation projects: 163 **(+138)**

The first value represents the project's status since its beginning, the second value (in brackets) represents the change compared to the previously reported status.

During the INDUSAC project:

- 164 Motivation Letters were approved by companies which equals 164 selected co-creation teams and 164 signed FSTP Declarations
- 163 co-creation teams submitted Solutions (1 team did not submit a Solution, see page 10)
- 159 Solutions were approved which equals 159 teams that received FSTP funds (4 teams submitted Solutions which were rejected, see pages 25-26)

In this deliverable (D3.5 - Monitoring and Evaluation Report) we refer to the entire co-creation process, starting with 164 teams with approved Motivation Letters, out of which 163 lead to submitted Solutions. Out of those, 159 were approved and received FSTP funds.

In the deliverable D3.3 (Odić et al. 2025b) we refer to the 164 teams since the title is “List of Company Challenges and **Selected Co-Creation Teams**”.

In deliverable D3.6 (FSTP Agreements with Students and Researchers; Odić et al. 2025a) we list only the 159 FSTP declarations that refer to co-creation teams that submitted Solutions which were approved and **received FSTP funding**.

III. LIST OF APPROVED SOLUTIONS

During the first period (11.2.2024-29.5.2024) of the INDUSAC call for students and researchers, with a cut-off date of 11 February 2024, 13 co-creation teams submitted solutions to the published challenges. Of these, 11 were approved and accepted based on the companies' selection (Table 1).

During the second period (30.5.2024-10.10.2024) of the INDUSAC call for students and researchers, with a cut-off date on 18 June 2024, companies approved eleven solutions, and the Evaluation Board approved one (Table 2).

During the third period (11.10.2024-10.07.2025) of the INDUSAC call for students and researchers, seven cut-offs were implemented, with the last one on 15 April 2025. Companies approved 122 solutions, and the Evaluation Board approved 13 (Table 3).

A complete list of summaries of approved INDUSAC co-creation solutions is available as a separate **deliverable D3.2.** "Summaries of Implemented Co-Creation Projects with Statistics on the Co-Creation Teams" [Odić et al. 2025c].

For a complete overview, the solutions that were submitted but not approved are also listed in the next chapter.

Table 1 : List of approved solutions in the first period (11.02.2024-29.05.2024) of the INDUSAC call for students and researchers

1	ReSoil® Web Revamp: Greening The Future By Restoring Degraded Land Worldwide (team 443055: Md Abdul Roshid, Mohammad Zeeshan, Elene Miminoshvili, Vineeta Taneja, Geeta Reemoh)
2	Innovative diversification: broadening horizons in die casting toolmaking (team 4000119: Ramin Mahmoudi, Idd Yunusu, Tanuj Namboodri, Moenes Benaissa, Wafae el majdoub)
3	Future approaches in organic skincare marketing initiatives (team 1800101: Nina Furman, Marko Jovanović, Ana Kolinger)
4	Future approaches in organic skincare marketing initiatives (team 4090101: Mihailo Milićević, Jana Delač, Aleksander Breznikar)
5	Robot fleet manager from open-source software (team 447068: Kawtar Dhaidah, Muhammad Hamza Daud, Moenes Benaissa, Ahmad Asaad, Ibrahim Shaglil)

Table 1 : (continued from previous page)

6	Removal of micropollutants from municipal wastewater (team 247090: Egzona Osmani, Nina Kovač, Ramin Mahmoudi, Selly Ayu Janetasari, Victor Kweku Ayertey)
7	Fun and easy to use "financial competence training & knowledge service" for people 50+ (team 5000105: Matevž Gortnar, Antonija Karin, Bogdan Buzadzic)
8	Battery electric vehicles - product opportunities (team 330066: Nina Kovač, Md Mehedi Hasan, Anja Svajger, Sabi William Konsago, Tim Hrovat, Tanuj Namboodri)
9	Pla:Fi The Innovative Pillow, Marketing Campaign (team 402093: Elena Orfanidou, Matevž Gortnar, Tanuj Namboodri, Tanja Luznar)
10	Transitioning From A Physical-Type Company To A Digital One (team 414063: Manal Abbes, Parnian Kashani, Makhosi Khuzawyo, Ekomobong Okopido, Ahlam Boubekri, Nouredine Hfaiedh)
11	Recycling Gazek Safety products (team 356074: Ramin Mahmoudi, Eszter Borsodi, Matevž Gortnar)

Table 2 : List of approved solutions from the second period (30.05.2024-10.10.2024) of the INDUSAC call for students and researchers.

12	Redesign and updating ENVIT's ReSoil® Website to Enhance Global Engagement and Accessibility (team 7500174: Angelina Apostoloska, Borko Petrevski, Stefana Spirkoska)
13	Inovative custom made hardwood floors (team 6990103: Mateja Srblijinović, Črt Švajger, Kosta Jovanovic)
14	Sustainability Challenge: Reducing Waste in Abrasive Materials Production (team 4470140: Muhammad Hamza Daud, Aimen Tanougast, Muhammad Ahmad, Wafae El majdoub, Idd Mohamed Yunusu)
15	Product labelling of the future (team 8550143: Tajda Hladnik, Alexander Delobel, Ana Arsovska)
16	Precious nanoparticles and their applications (team 312097: Mariem Zouari, Lei Han, Ana Gubenšek, Amina Selmanović, Wojciech Pajerski, Rene Alexander Herrera Diaz)

Table 2 : (continued from previous page)

17	New ideas to natural skincare marketing approaches (team 4090132: Jana Delač, Aleksander Breznikar, Jelena Grujicic)
18	New ideas to natural skincare marketing approaches (team 1800132: Nina Furman, Gabriela Suša, Sara Epet)
19	Advancements in Orthopedic and Dental Implant Surface Treatments (team 649049: Alexia Ecaterina Cârstea, Dan Laptoiu, Florin Miculescu, Lucian Toma Ciocan, Marco Truccato, Silviu Colis)
20	Aluminum oxide powder with active surface to be used as catalyst in other chemical processes (team 273053: Anja Svajger, Lenart Žežlina, Margareth Carla Perez Pariguana, Nina Kovač, Sabi William Konsago, Yasin Sahin)
21	Marketing campaign for green mobile solution RolUet (team 302081: Luka Rakovič, Elena Orfanidou, Hanif Ahmad, Tanja Luznar)
22	Developing virtual bar caffe of the future (team 778078: Zainab Fatima, Lali Kurdadze, Eda Nur KAÇAKÇI)
23	Redesign and updating ENVIT's ReSoil® Website to Enhance Global Engagement and Accessibility (team 4430174: Mohammad Zeeshan, Md Abdul Roshid, Elene Miminoshvili, Geeta Reemoh, Zainab Ftima)

Table 3 : List of approved solutions from the third period (11.10.2024-10.07.2025) of the INDUSAC call for students and researchers.

24	Tennis academy assistant (team 2830167: Ajša Džindo, Antonija Karin, Gašper Škof, Lev Kiar Avberšek)
25	Smart Tools (team 7770139: Abedin S. M. Ashik, Ahmed Faisal, Mritika Roy, IDD MOHAMED YUNUSU)
26	Marketing campaign for metalized/conductive yarns (team 482069: Ashik Abedin, Ahmed Faisal, Mritika Roy)
27	SWOT Analysis Of An Energy Efficient Office Building In Operation In A County Capital Of Hungary (team 958043: Haniye Shojaee, Gašper Gortnar, Margareth Carla Perez Pariguana)
28	Marketing Campaign For An Energy Efficient Office Building In A Hungarian County Capital (team 656042: Gašper Gortnar, Haniye Shojaee, Kosta Jovanovic)

Table 3 : *continued from previous page*

29	Optimizing ENVIT's ReSoil® Website for Enhanced Performance, Branding, and User Experience (team 7500196: Angelina Apostoloska, Borko Petrevski, Stefana Spirkoska)
30	New Ideas To Natural Skincare Marketing Approaches (team 9340132: Ilyas El Bourari, Jasna Smilkov, Matic Krašovic)
31	Project 3in1: Innovative Approaches to Discovering Consumer Needs. An In-Depth Detergent Market Overview and Trend Analysis (team 9670144: Dino Andreevski, Jana Jovanoska, Jovana Asterija Nakova)
32	Marketing And Selling Campaigns Based On Market Research (team 9650145: Dino Andreevski, Jana Jovanoska, Jovana Asterija Nakova)
33	Green Efficiency: Designing the Future Marketing Campaign for Connect IQ (team 9440173: Ilyas El Bourari, Jasna Smilkov, Matic Krašovic)
34	New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare (team 4090202: Aleksander Breznikar, Jana Delač, Jelena Grujicic)
35	New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare (team 1800202: Gabriela Suša, Nina Furman, Sara Epet)
36	Increasing Social Media Popularity In The Non-Profit Sector (team 955044: Haniye Shojaee, Meta Švagelj, Ujmir Uka)
37	Unlocking Market Potential: Comprehensive Analysis of Healthy Ice Creams for the Health-Conscious Consumer (team 9090183: Ilyas El Bourari, Jasna Smilkov, Maksim Dovečar, Matic Krašovic)
38	Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations (team 10420201: Lučka Kaligarič, Martina Mileva, Marija Ristovska, Vanja Angjelovikj, Marko Arsov)
39	Alveus kitchen sink: The centerpiece of your kitchen (team 4990191: Antonija Karin, Marko Lui, Andrea Anna Milin)
40	Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations (team 2230201: Karla Marinović, Marko Jovanović, Sandra Mikić, Olivera Delic, Tamara Attard)

Table 3 : (continued from previous page)

41	Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations (team 10550201: Damjan Georgievski, Iva Edrovska, Kostadin Mitkov)
42	AI Assistants: Automating and Streamlining Engineering Processes (team 2730197: Anja Svajger, Martin Georgievski, Stefanos Heikki Panagiotou, Tim Hrovat, Timotej Šuman)
43	Young People Live Sustainably (team 9510179: Mohamad Ali, Pavel Aftimiciuc, Piotr Mazur, Nasibakhon Rasulova)
44	Competitor Analysis of ClimateLaunchpad (EIT Climate-KIC) (team 9620176: Egzona Osmani, Maša Kralj, Md Mehedi Hasan)
45	New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare (team 11450202: Dragan Jovanovski, Sabrina Jurkošek, Maša Ćorović)
46	Autonomous Roof Structure for Drone Hub (team 11520209: Ajhan Skenderoski, João Pedro da Silva Moreira dos Santos, Slavica Dimkoska)
47	ReSoil® Web Revamp: Greening The Future By Restoring Degraded Land Worldwide (team 878055: João Pedro da Silva Moreira dos Santos, Tamara Trajkovska, Zdravko Brdarovski)
48	Gaining Momentum Through Effective Marketing (team 9240150: Hanif Ahmad, Julija Miladinovska, Lucijana Kraljević)
49	Developing a Smart Color Identification Online/Mobile App (team 4610193: Ibrahim Shaglil, Md Fahim Harun, Valentina Temnik)
50	Development and Execution of a Social Media Strategy for Tower Spa (team 8570291: Ana Arsovska, Sanket Singh, Stefan Stojanovski)
51	New sustainable service offerings in a family-owned restaurant (team 9550293: Mohamed Amine El Bourari, Luka Polanič, Vanesa Efremova)
52	New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare (team 11300202: Adrijana Minić, Gašper Korošec, Marija Koleva, Minela Kaltak)
53	Protective working equipment (team 4160181: Mayssae Choukri, Makhosi Khuzwayo, Sahar Hattab)

Table 3 :.(continued from previous page)

54	Researching Innovative Approaches for Enhancing Skincare Formulation (team 2230311: Karla Marinović, Marko Jovanović, Sandra Mikić, Olivera Delic, Tamara Attard)
55	Implementation of AI systems in the metal processing industry (small and medium sized production) (team 4610203: Ibrahim Shaglif, Kawtar Dhaidah, Moenes Benaissa, Nouredine Hfaiedh, Wafae El Majdoub)
56	Researching Innovative Approaches for Enhancing Skincare Formulation (team 10550311: Damjan Georgievski, Iva Edrovaska, Kostadin Mitkov)
57	Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare (team 11450300: Dragan Jovanovski, Sabrina Jurkošek, Maša Ćorović)
58	Recycling 3D printing waste (team 11430230: Faustin Habimana, Huzaifa Tahir, Budagodage Lisani Nimira Nadeeshani, Nima E. Gorji)
59	Marketing And Selling Campaigns Based On Market Research (team 8730145: Shreyash Singh, Yeliena Bemeshchuk, Sviatoslav Novosad, Dorina Péntek)
60	Project Brief for IKEA: Future-Driven Market Insights for Furniture & Home Furnishing Accessories in Slovenia (team 9650247: Dino Andreevski, Jana Jovanoska, Jovana Asterija Nakova)
61	Virtual Bar Caffee: Functional Development, Optimization and SEO Strategy (team 11830289: Hoimonti Choudhury, Ritoprovo Roy, Lali Kurdadze, Pradyumna Kapure, Md Farid)
62	Innovative Financial Health Reporting for Companies (team 12300190: Tea Papec, Una Sekulović, Zdravko Brdarovski)
63	Gaining Momentum Through Effective Marketing (team 11450150: Ivana Kisin, Maša Ćorović, Vasil Stojanov)
64	WATER AND ENERGY SAVING IN AQUATICS CENTRES FACILITIES (team 12120165: Ajhan Skenderoski, Daniel Pereira, Slavica Dimkoska)
65	Airbridge Go To Market (team 11520296: Ajhan Skenderoski, Filip Bojinović, Slavica Dimkoska)
66	Young People Live Sustainably (team 11820179: Ariana Sadiku, Ana Dragić, Md Fahim Harun)

Table 3 : (continued from previous page)

67	Researching Innovative Approaches for Enhancing Skincare Formulation (team 10420311: Lučka Kaligarič, Martina Mileva, Marija Ristovska, Vanja Angjelovikj, Marko Arsov)
68	AI Avatar Interactive Learning System for Cutting-Edge EdTech Platform (team 12310123: Nik Kos, Olha Sanko, Viktor Tikhonov, Viktoriya Tonoyan, Viktor Bortsevich, Yuehan John)
69	Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare (team 4410300: Ahlam Boubekri, Ahmad Asaad, Parnian Kashani)
70	Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare (team 11650300: Ivana Kisin, Md Fahim Harun, Tanja Gošnjak)
71	Project Brief for IKEA: Designing the Marketing Campaign for Sustainability-Conscious Consumers (team 4410255: Ahlam Boubekri, Dániel Simon Berkesi, Parnian Kashani)
72	Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion (team 13590304: Blerina Hasani, Eva Simonič, Gjorgi Andonovski)
73	BossFacade-EcoFacade (team 13680258: Alaa Abbadi, Iva Dimitrievska, Nikolina Landeka)
74	Crack the code: Help us connect with the next gen of learners online (team 9510233: Mohamad Ali Hijazi, Pavel Aftimiciuc, Nasibakhon Rasulova, Zahraa Hijazi)
75	Bioprinting - future technology for tissues and drugs (team 13380231: Evgenija Kolovska, Juš Smole, Tjaša Šentjunc)
76	Educational Center at Greenagro (team 12670227: Diana Vicente, Filipe Santos, Muhammad Ahsan Yaseen)
77	Illuminating the Invisible: UV-visible Marking on Recycled Paper (team 10030313: Martina Mileva, Marija Ristovska, Vanja Angjelovikj, Marko Arsov)
78	Forecasting and predicting customer's behaviour and their ability for repaying their obligations (team 9200237: Ivana Kisin, Mustafa Mustafa Bekmezci, Stefanos Heikki Panagiotou, Yasin Sahin)
79	Internationalisation of Greenagro products and services (team 12980226: Lucija Kostanić, Maksim Dovečar, Muhammad Ahsan Yaseen, Mirjana Nedelkovska)

Table 3 : (continued from previous page)

80	Innovative Biocomposite Product Using Industrial Hemp Fibers for High-Value Sustainable Applications (team 13390235: Aleksandra Vrkačević, Gjorgi Andonovski, Marko Gorenak, Leja Rebolj)
81	Innovative B2B Solutions Through Cross-Industry Collaboration Challenge (team 12640301: Ahmad Asaad, Najwa El Majdoub, Kawtar Dhaidah, Nouredine Hfaiedh)
82	Innovative Biocomposite Product Using Industrial Hemp Fibers for High-Value Sustainable Applications (team 12450235: Adam Grzywaczyk, Branislav Trudic, Emma Olmi, Natalia Burlaga, Zuzanna Styrna, Wojciech Smutek)
83	Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion (team 7580304: Gabriela Suša, Jelena Grujicic, Sara Epet, Tal Ben Shalom)
84	MCO Marketing Campaign (Marketing Campaign) (team 7430170: Blerina Hasani, Gašper Gortnar, Andreja Šormaz)
85	Educational LinkedIn Campaign: Recycling Facts, Myths, and Proper Waste Sorting Practices (team 13620214: Gustavo Raiser Micheli, Jiara Laine Montaño, Kornkanok Keardsap, Pedr Monteiro)
86	Eco-Friendly Returnable Packaging (team 12670240: Ana Dragić, Ariana Sadiku, Filipe Santos)
87	Product Utilizing Post-Production Re grind (team 4470239: Edita Dvořáková, Najwa El Majdoub, Muhammad Hamza Daud)
88	Eco-Friendly Returnable Packaging (team 12540240: Edita Dvořáková, Georgios Koutsikas, Shubhanshu Singh)
89	Innovative Marketing and Sales Campaigns of the Future for HROPOL A. Horeczy Sp. K. (team 12140317: Ivana Koleva, Anđela Mrđa, Vasil Stojanov)
90	Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare (team 14410300: Muhammed Hanbal Abdullatheef, Nadja Klimenta, Urša Švigelj)
91	Crack the code: Help us connect with the next gen of learners online (team 13930233: Ana Taseva, Eva Toplišek, Isidora Marković)
92	Young People Live Sustainably (team 12540179: Edita Dvořáková, Georgios Koutsikas, Shubhanshu Singh)

Table 3 : (continued from previous page)

93	Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector (team 14640292: Amadea Iva Delopst, Gabriele Grilli, Kosta Jovanovic)
94	Young People Live Sustainably (team 12670179: Filipe Santos, Maksim Dovečar, Muhammad Ahsan Yaseen)
95	Post-production process automation: Designing a system for the automatic removal of supports and surface smoothing of 3D prints (team 11430232: Farbod Rokni, Gülcan BAL, Huzaifa Tahir)
96	AEPAP: From Advanced Engineering Prototypes To Actual Production (team 11430180: Fenteng Eric Agyei Owusu, Huzaifa Tahir, Budagodage Lisani Nimira Nadeeshani)
97	Business plan for a digital tool on healthy urban planning (team 13980169: Muhammed Hanbal Abdullatheef, Nikolina Topić, Sara Slamnik)
98	Innovation Ecosystem Matchmaking Platform: Expert-Innovator Connection Hub for Technology Commercialization (team 15090308: Idrissa Maiga, Luka Taslak, Norina Vigh)
99	ReSoil® Website Digital Optimization, SEO Strategy, and User Engagement (team 7500310: Angelina Apostoloska, Borko Petrevski, Stefana Spirkoska)
100	Elevating Tower Spa's Brand Through Engaging Digital Content (team 8570350: Ana Arsovska, Sanket Singh, Stefan Stojanovski)
101	Young People Live Sustainably (team 13640179: Gustavo Raiser Micheli, Jiara Laine Montaño, Kornkanok Keardsap, Pedro Monteiro)
102	Project Brief for IKEA: Future-Driven Market Insights for Furniture & Home Furnishing Accessories in Slovenia (team 14010247: Ivan Andonovski, Eva Toplišek, Nikolina Topić)
103	Hoply: Safe, and affordable rides for kids, simplifying after-school transportation for families (team 15290335: Igor Arsov, Gordana Petkovska, Mia Jakimovska)
104	Office of the future: tech to wellbeing (team 15230164: Enrico Rigamonti, Godfried Adaba, George-Marian Tudose, Karina Trelles, Nathaniel Amoah)
105	Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector (team 15380292: Farhan Ali, Sana Ullah, Jelena Pecelj)

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106	Project Brief for IKEA: Designing the Marketing Campaign for Sustainability-Conscious Consumers (team 15150255: Vladimir Georgievski, Emili Koshulcheva, Saram Mitkovska, Sofija Stojanova, Toshe Dimov)
107	Personalized Innovation Funding Alert System: Intelligent Newsletter Platform for Research Competitions (team 15090307: Idrissa Maiga, Luka Taslak, Norina Vigh)
108	Energy-related regulation scenarios in Europe in 2030 (team 14540288: Alina Maria Vaduva, Daniel Balsalobre Lorente, Muhammet Demirbilek, Mirela Panait, Samantha Reid, Riccardo Bigi)
109	AI-Powered EU Grant Advisory Platform Development for Scientific Innovations (team 15090306: Idrissa Maiga, Sonay Karaaslan, Norina Vigh)
110	Development Of A Chlorine-Free Water Disinfection System (team 13560109: Egzona Osmani, Kassie Tesfaye Mengie, Zahraa Hijazi)
111	New sustainable service offerings in a family-owned restaurant (team 14410293: Muhammed Hanbal Abdullatheef, Nadja Klimenta, Urša Švagelj)
112	Office of the future: tech to wellbeing (team 15290164: Igor Arsov, Gordana Petkovska, Mia Jakimovska, Jana Belichevska)
113	Development Of A Chlorine-Free Water Disinfection System (team 2710109: Izabel Peternel, Nelby Brañez Ramos, Md Mehedi Hasan)
114	Bioprinting - future technology for tissues and drugs (team 6490231: Alexandru Ginga – Grigorescu, Alexia Ecaterina Cârstea, João Malta Barbosa, Lucian Toma Ciocan, Marco Truccato, Robert Ancuceanu)
115	Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector (team 15590292: Andrej Kasura: Benzaid Salma, Fatima-Ezzahra Mabchour)
116	Creating a financial product for Gen Z investors – "Gip-Z" (team 13830347: Berat Sinani, Jovana Ivanovic, Matej Međugorac)
117	Constructing a Creative Marketing Campaign to Attract Macedonian Generation Z Investors in Financial Services (team 13830329: Ivan Andonovski, Jovana Ivanovic, Matej Međugorac)
118	Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector (team 16170292: Lindrit Krasniqi, Lucijana Kraljevic, Julija Miladinovska)

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119	Cellulose Reinvented (team 15810346: Andrzej Baziak, Anja Dujković, Dragana Stevic)
120	Developing & Testing a Low-Cost Sustainable Insulation or Monitoring Solution for Temperature-Sensitive Logistics (team 15760354: Md Mazedur Rahman, Pritam Chowdhury, Swastika Roy)
121	Innovative Skincare Formulation: Advanced Research and Optimization (team 10360348: Karla Marinović, Olivera Delić, Sandra Mikić, Tamara Attard)
122	Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector (team 15220292: Maciej Zagórski, Nika Horvat, Patricia Pavleković)
123	The Global Perfusion Gaming Tournament (team 1522094: Maciej Zagórski, Nika Horvat, Patricia Pavleković)
124	Creating a financial product for Gen Z investors – "Gip-Z" (team 12190347: Kristijan Stefanoski, Tea Papec, Una Sekulović)
125	New sustainable service offerings in a family-owned restaurant (team 14880293: Ivan Križič, Lindrit Krasniqi, Pia Popović)
126	Young People Live Sustainably (team 14530179: Annalisa Musto, Claudio Pontillo, Filomena Izzo, Ozlem Ozdemir, Mubabela Ndaye)
127	Inovative Custom Made Hardwood Floors (team 14880103: Ivan Križič, Pia Popović, Raheleh Soltanibahrehand)
128	Inovative Custom Made Hardwood Floors (team 15790103: Md Mazedur Rahman, Pritam Chowdhury, Swastika Roy)
129	Young People Live Sustainably (team 15800179: Anja Kumer Lapornik, Mohammed Aslam, Mohammed Adnan Bellypady Abdulla)
130	Digital Music Education Innovation (team 15220213: Maciej Zagórski, Nika Horvat, Patricia Pavleković)
131	Innovative Social Media Strategies for Natural Skincare (team 11300300: Adrijana Minić, Marija Koleva, Minela Kaltak)
132	Creating a B2B Marketing Campaign for High-Quality decoration cosmetic packaging and plastic components various industries (team 14700364: Ivana Koleva, Anđela Mrđa, Nikolche Gjorgjievski)

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133	Developing Sustainable Event Services and Methodology for Restaurants (team 12980294: Erik Curk, Lucija Kostanić, Mirjana Nedelkovska)
134	Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion (team 15620304: Anabela Jelača, Ivan Atanasov, Nikolche Gjorgjievski)
135	Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion (team 8700304: Dragan Jovanovski, Sabrina Jurkošek, Mirjana Nedelkovska)
136	Creating a financial product for Gen Z investors – "Gip-Z" (team 3990347: Mohamed Amine El Bourari, Hanif Ahmad, Vanesa Efremova)
137	Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector (team 8730292: Dorina Péntek, Sani Ahmed, Shreyash Singh, Theodore Newman)
138	Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion (team 15520304: Eszter Borsodi, Daniel Gojković, Nadja Klimenta)
139	Innovative Marketing Campaign to Attract Tourist in Hospitality Sector (team 15630292: Anabela Jelača, Ivan Atanasov, Nikolche Gjorgjievski)
140	Young People Live Sustainably (team 14030179: Boban Nikolov, Guillermo McCarthy Valderrama, Pilar García García)
141	Airbridge Go To Market (team 15380296: Farhan Ali, Sana Ullah, Jelena Pecelj)
142	Microelectronic Industry PCB boards recycling (PCB-REC) (team 13680345: Andrzej Baziak, Nikolina Landeka, Tijana Kremenović)
143	Eco-Friendly Solvents for Cosmetics: Harnessing the Power of DES (team 10550349: Damjan Georgievski, Iva Edrovska, Kostadin Mitkov)
144	Innovative Financial Health Reporting for Companies (team 16120190: Ana Barišić, Kristijan Stefanoski, Natália Konkolyová)
145	Review of New Restrictions on Product Packaging and Labeling and Analysis of Impact on the Market (team 14350355: Berat Sinani, Jelena Pecelj, Sara Slamnik)
146	Croatian market research regarding the sale of concrete products (team 13830312: Berat Sinani, Jovana Ivanović, Matej Međugorac)
147	Green Efficiency: Designing the Future Marketing Campaign for Connect IQ" (team 16190173: Dounia Aamoum, Antonija Andonovski, Andrey Hilyadnikov)

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148	Shaping the Future of Machine Efficiency: Understanding Customer Needs for OEE Optimization (team 14130199: Angela Andonovski, Federico Centofanti, Pepa Guerrero Mayo)
149	Airbridge Go To Market (team 14640296: Amadea Iva Delopst, Mohammed Aslam, Mohammed Adnan Bellipady Abdulla)
150	Creating Large-Scale Databases of Tool Companies, Wholesalers, Stores, and Garden Centers in Europe, the Middle East, and Asia, Along with Decision-Maker Identification and B2B Customer Segmentation (team 15230341: Alina Maria Vaduva, Enrico Rigamonti, Godfried Adaba, George-Marian Tudose, Karina Trelles, Nathaniel Amoah)
151	Market analysis and trendspotting of automotive lighting products with focus on end customer (team 16190161: Dounia Aamoum, Antonija Andonovski, Andrey Hilyadnikov)
152	Marketing campaign for metal-forming defects sensors (team 16190261: Dounia Aamoum, Antonija Andonovski, Andrey Hilyadnikov)
153	Creating Large-Scale Databases of Tool Companies, Wholesalers, Stores, and Garden Centers in Europe, the Middle East, and Asia, Along with Decision-Maker Identification and B2B Customer Segmentation (team 14030341: Boban Nikolov, Guillermo McCarthy Valderrama, Pilar García García)
154	Enhancing digital marketing of a small International Fiscal & Law Firm (team 14030208: Boban Nikolov, Guillermo McCarthy Valderrama, Pilar García García)
155	Constructing a Creative Marketing Campaign to Attract Macedonian Generation Z Investors in Financial Services (team 15590347: Andrej Kasura, Salma Benzaid, Fatima Ezzahra Mabchour)
156	MARKETING CAMPAIGN OF THE FUTURE (team 15830205: Ilyas El, Izabel Peternel, Uzair Qazi)
157	MARKETING CAMPAIGN OF THE FUTURE (team 15850205: Anja Kumer Lapornik, Mohammed Aslam, Mohammed Adnan Bellypady Abdulla)
158	Competitor Analysis of ClimateLaunchpad (EIT Climate-KIC) (team 15320176: Roshid Md Abdul, Avrupa Birligi, Besmira Fejzullahu, Tamás Németh)
159	Creative Visual and Content Strategy for Skincare and Spa Promotion (team 12600304: Mohamed Amine El Bourari, Luka Polanič, Vanesa Efremova)

IV. LIST OF SUBMITTED BUT NOT APPROVED SOLUTIONS

After reviewing the feedback from the companies, it was observed that certain solutions had not undergone a thorough evaluation process. In cases where the company either failed to evaluate them despite multiple reminders, the solutions were rejected, or the company became inactive, the Evaluation Board took over the responsibility of evaluating the solutions. The Evaluation Board meticulously reviewed the submitted documentation for the solutions using the Evaluation of Solution template (Annex 1), a tool also provided to companies for their independent evaluation of submitted solutions, which played a crucial role in determining eligibility for financial support for students.

Comprised of eight members, the Evaluation Board conducted individual assessments of the submitted solutions, which were not evaluated due to previously mentioned reasons, leading to a collective final evaluation.

During the first period (11.02.2024-29.05.2024) of the INDUSAC's call for students and researchers, the Evaluation Board was tasked with evaluating two solutions. The Board's final assessment revealed that the solutions presented by "Age-friendly banking and fraud prevention" (Team ID: 484098) and "Recycling Gazek Safety products—responsibility for all, for everything" (Team ID: 366074) did not meet the threshold for FSTP eligibility based on their overall scores. The reason for this was that the solutions did not adequately fulfil the core business and technical requirements outlined in the challenge (listed in Table 4).

The Evaluation Board was tasked with assessing one solution, "Redesign and updating ENVIT's ReSoil® Website to Enhance Global Engagement and Accessibility" (team 4430174), obtained from the second period (30.05.2024-10.10.2024) of the INDUSAC's call for students and researchers. This solution has been officially approved, as it successfully met the necessary criteria by surpassing the minimum threshold required for FSTP eligibility (listed in Table 2).

The Evaluation Board was tasked during the third period (11.10.2024-10.07.2025) of the INDUSAC project with evaluating 15 solutions (10 that companies did not review and five that companies rejected). The Board's final assessment revealed that 13 submitted solutions met the necessary criteria by exceeding the minimum threshold required for FSTP eligibility and were approved (listed in Table 3).

During the third period of the INDUSAC project, two solutions were rejected due to challenges related to team verification and identification. The first solution, submitted for "Young People Live Sustainably" (team 10150179), was rejected by the company due to suspicions of fraudulent representation by team members, who, upon request, failed to produce satisfactory identification documents (listed in Table 4).

The second solution, submitted for "Office of the Future: Tech to Wellbeing" (team 10150164), was initially accepted by the company. However, upon request, team members failed to provide satisfactory identification documents, resulting in disqualification (listed in Table 4).

Table 4 : List of submitted but not approved solutions through the entire duration (11.02.2024-10.07.2025) of the INDUSAC's call for students and researchers.

1	Age-friendly banking and fraud prevention (Team: 484098)	1 st period (11.02.2024-29.05.2024)
2	Recycling Gazek Safety products (Team: 366074)	1 st period (11.02.2024-29.05.2024)
3	Young People Live Sustainably (Team 10150179)	3 rd period (11.10.2024-10.07.2025)
4	Office of the future: tech to wellbeing (Team 10150164)	3 rd period (11.10.2024-10.07.2025)

V. ANALYSIS OF QUESTIONNAIRE / SURVEY RESULTS

Before the start of each co-creation project, during the first, second, and third period of the INDUSAC call for students and researchers, the co-creation team members received information about the approval of their Motivation Letter. At this point, each team member was asked to fill out a survey to evaluate his / her skill levels.

After the end of the co-creation project the co-creation team submitted its challenge solution. Following this, the co-creation team members were requested again to complete a comprehensive questionnaire evaluating the specific skills they utilized, acquired, and improved throughout the challenge.

The questionnaires designed for students and researchers aimed to gather important information regarding the clarity of the co-creation process and the level of satisfaction derived from it. Additionally, the questionnaires aimed to assess the participants' skills both before and after completing the challenge.

After co-creation teams successfully submitted their solutions to the challenges, companies were requested to participate in a thorough questionnaire aimed at evaluating the effectiveness of the INDUSAC process and platform. The questionnaire also delved into assessing the quality and impact of the received solutions.

The data obtained from questionnaire analysis was used to improve the INDUSAC process and the methodology elements.

1. Students & researchers

The questionnaires that the co-creation team members received before the start of the co-creation project and after the end of the individual co-creation project were used to monitor their readiness and assess the impact of their participation. They aimed to evaluate the teams' skills, experiences, and satisfaction. An example of the questionnaire for co-creation team members before and after is given in the report's Annex 2.

During the first period (11.02.2024-29.05.2024) of the INDUSAC call for students and researchers, 82 questionnaire responses were received before the start of the co-creation project and after the first cut-off date (11 February 2024). However, 11 of them were not completed and were excluded from the evaluation, leaving 71 fully completed responses (Figure 1). After the submission of solutions for the first cut-off date, each member of the co-creation team received the same questionnaire, resulting in 83 responses. Unfortunately, 27 of these responses were inadequately filled out and were excluded from the analysis, resulting in 56 valid responses (Figure 1).

During the second period (30.05.2024-10.10.2024) of the INDUSAC call for students and researchers, 70 questionnaire responses were received at the start of the co-creation project

and after the second cut-off date for the call (18 June 2024). However, nine were not completed and therefore excluded from the evaluation, leaving 61 fully completed responses (Figure 1). After the solutions were submitted for the second cut-off date, each member of the co-creation team received the same questionnaire, which led to 63 responses. Unfortunately, 19 of these responses were inadequately filled out and were not considered in the analysis, resulting in 44 valid responses (see Figure 1).

During the third period (11.10.2024-10.07.2025) of the INDUSAC call for students and researchers, 462 questionnaire responses were received before the start of the co-creation project. However, 32 of them were not completed and were excluded from the evaluation, leaving 430 fully completed responses (Figure 1). After the submission of solutions for the last cut-off date, each member of the co-creation team received the same questionnaire, resulting in 562 responses. Unfortunately, 131 of these responses were inadequately filled out and were excluded from the analysis, resulting in 431 valid responses (Figure 1).

Overall, during the entire period of the INDUSAC, a total of 614 questionnaires were received before the start of the co-creation projects. However, due to incomplete responses, 52 of these questionnaires were classified as non-evaluable. Following the submission of solutions, the number of received questionnaires was increased to 708. Nevertheless, 177 of these were subsequently discarded because they were filled out inadequately (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 : Evaluability of questionnaires after the cut-off date for students and researchers.

1.1. Skills (before & after)

For the rating, Likert Scale was used to quantitatively assess opinions, attitudes, or behaviours as follows:

Scaling: 1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good

There were 17 factors identified linked to soft skills in order to examine the readiness of the co-creation team members in the initial entering phase, these were:

- Communication skills
- Negotiation
- Results oriented thinking
- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Working with international teams
- English (language skills)

Figure 2 shows the team members' responses in percentages for the first, second, and third periods of the INDUSAC calls. Due to the large amount of data, Figure 2 has been divided into three parts to enhance clarity and ensure the information is easy to read and interpret.

From the survey analysis, it was observed that students and researchers reported their skills to be quite high even before they started the co-creation projects. During the first period (11.02.2024-29.05.2024) of the INDUSAC call, their average skills level was approximately 86 % (before) and 90 % (after).

During the second period (30.05.2024-10.10.2024), the co-creation teams displayed consistent skill levels comparable to those achieved during the first period of the INDUSAC project. Before the second period of the INDUSAC project's implementation, the teams' skill levels were approximately 86 %. After participating in the project, these skill levels improved to around 89 %.

During the third period (11.10.2024-10.07.2025), their average skill level shows the most significant difference. The average skill level was approximately 85% before, which increased to 90% after.

The overall progress is shown in Figure 2 (parts 1-3), which highlights an average skill enhancement of over 4 %. This evaluation showed that, although students and researchers initially possessed a strong skill set, their competencies were further enhanced throughout the INDUSAC co-creation projects.

Figure 2 : Skills of the co-creation team members before the co-creation project and after the co-creation project solution submission. *(continued on next page)*

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Figure 2 : Skills of the co-creation team members before the co-creation project and after the co-creation project solution submission.

The skills that initially received lower evaluations (below 80 %) showed the most significant improvements, particularly in negotiation and conflict management, as well as experience working with companies and international teams (see Figure 3). Figure 3 has been divided into two parts to enhance clarity and facilitate easier reading and comprehension.

During the first period of the INDUSAC call, surveys revealed that negotiation skills increased by over 7 % and conflict management skills improved by more than 6 %. The most significant increases, however, were in experience working with companies and collaborating with international teams, which rose by 9 % and 15 %, respectively (see Figure 3, part 1).

Surveys from the second period of the INDUSAC call revealed that negotiation and conflict management skills increased by over 6 %. Meanwhile, experience in working with companies and collaborating with international teams increased by 10 % and 9 %, respectively (see Figure 3, part 1).

In the third period of the INDUSAC call, negotiation and conflict management skills were similar to those in the first period, increasing by over 7 % and 6 % respectively. Meanwhile, experience working with companies and collaborating with international teams increased by 9 % (see Figure 3, part 1).

The survey revealed that additional skill competencies showed measurable improvement over time. In the first two periods, gains in key areas—Creativity, Critical Thinking, Time Management, and Leadership—were relatively modest, with increases of less than 3 % (see Figure 3, part 2). In contrast, the third period showed a significant improvement, with gains of 5–7 % across these skill categories (see Figure 3, part 2). This notable progress is likely due to a combination of factors, including a larger number of survey participants, exposure to more complex challenges, and evolving team dynamics, all of which fostered deeper engagement and more effective development. Overall, the average skill score increased from 86 % to 88 %, with the third period making the most significant contribution to this positive trend.

The survey evaluation findings highlight that students and researchers derive significant benefits from engaging in collaborative work with companies and participating in international team projects. This hands-on experience during the co-creation initiative not only enhances their practical skills but also fosters a deeper understanding of real-world working. These collaborative interactions are fundamental to achieving one of the primary goals of the INDUSAC project, which seeks to bridge academic knowledge with industry practice.

Figure 3 : Improved skills in negotiation and conflict management, experience working with companies, and working with international teams of the members of the co-creation teams (part 1) and Creativity, Critical Thinking, Time Management, and Leadership (part 2) (before and after the co-creation project)

Figure 4 displays the progress of the skill development of co-creation teams before and after the INDUSAC call. The numbers on the x-axis represent the identification numbers assigned to each team. These identifiers are simply labels and do not imply any order or ranking. *Due to the large amount of data, Figure 4 has been divided into five parts to enhance clarity and ensure the information is easy to see and understand.*

At the level of co-creation teams, there were visible improvements and progress in skill development, with an average increase of at least 5 % (Figure 4, part 1) during the first period of the INDUSAC call.

This trend of improvement in skill development for co-creation teams was also observed during the second period of the INDUSAC call, with an average increase of at least 4 % (Figure 4, part 1). In the third period of the INDUSAC call (Figure 4, parts 2-5), visible improvements and progress in skill development were observed, with an average increase of at least 5 %.

Moreover, 16 % of all teams successfully demonstrated an overall skill enhancement of more than 10 %, clearly indicating a significant positive impact of the INDUSAC project on a substantial portion of participants.

Figure 4 : Skill development in co-creation teams of the members of the co-creation teams (before and after the co-creation project). *(continued on next page)*

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Figure 4 : Skill development in co-creation teams of the members of the co-creation teams (before and after the co-creation project). (continued on next page)

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Figure 4 : Skill development in co-creation teams of the members of the co-creation teams (before and after the co-creation project).

All relevant parts for this deliverable D3.5 of the **Objective 5** “At least 70 % of students and researchers participating reporting at least one core professional transversal and entrepreneurial skill having been significantly developed by participating in the piloting of the INDUSAC IAC mechanism.” can be **confirmed** for all periods (1st, 2nd and 3rd) of the INDUSAC project's call for students and researchers **since over 87 % of students and**

researchers participating reporting a Negotiation and Conflict management, Experience in working with companies and international teams skills, as well as Creativity, Critical Thinking, Time Management, and Leadership having been significantly developed by participating in the piloting of the INDUSAC IAC mechanism.

All relevant parts for this deliverable D3.5 of the **Objective 7** “To improve this set of skills (transversal and entrepreneurial skills (communication, negotiation, results oriented, responsibility, creativity, planning skills, analytical thinking, among others) in students and researchers in at least 30 % compared to before the beginning of the project, allowing them to rapidly expand their skillset in a short period of time and to find themselves more prepared for the business environment.” can be **confirmed for** all periods (1st, 2nd and 3rd) of the INDUSAC project's call for students and researchers **since 90 % out of 531 students and researchers** who filled out the questionnaire (taking into account that a given individual filled the questionnaire for each team separately) **have reported improvements of skills.**

The key performance indicator (KPI) for the students was to ensure that at least 80 % of students were likely or highly likely to recommend participating in the programme to their peers. It has been **confirmed** that all periods (1st, 2nd and 3rd) of the INDUSAC project's call for students and researchers, **90 % in the 1st period, 91 % in the 2nd period and 94 % in the 3rd period of students stated that they are likely or highly likely to recommend participation** in the programme to their peers.

1.2. Satisfaction (before & after)

Figure 5 presents the co-creation team members satisfaction with INDUSAC's process and platform before and after the co-creation project solution submission. During the first period (11.02.2024-29.05.2024), co-creation teams expressed overall satisfaction of over 77 % with the INDUSAC process and 81 % with the INDUSAC platform.

In the second period (30.05.2024-10.10.2024), the satisfaction levels increased significantly, with over 86 % of the co-creation teams expressing satisfaction with the INDUSAC process and 87 % with the INDUSAC platform (see Figure 5). This represents an increase of more than 9 % for the INDUSAC process and 6 % for the INDUSAC platform compared to the results from the first period.

In the third period (11.10.2024-10.07.2025), overall satisfaction increased further to 92 % with the INDUSAC process and 91 % with the INDUSAC platform. This represents an additional increase of 6 % for the INDUSAC process and 4 % for the INDUSAC platform compared to the second period.

Overall, the data reveals a consistent and meaningful upward trend in user satisfaction across all three periods. The steady increases in satisfaction with both the process and platform suggest that ongoing improvements, platform refinements, and experience gained by participants throughout the project cycles contributed to a more effective and user-

friendly co-creation environment. These results highlight the growing acceptance and perceived value of the INDUSAC approach among its users, indicating strong potential for continued adoption and impact in future implementations.

Figure 5 : Satisfaction with the process and platform for co-creation teams.

1.3. Additional feedback

The data in Figure 6 shows the frequency of meetings conducted by co-creation teams and companies. It can be seen that meetings between co-creation teams and the company's representative occurred regularly during the duration of the first and second periods of the INDUSAC call for the co-creation project. However, it was observed that during the second period of the INDUSAC call for the co-creation project, co-creation teams and company representatives met more regularly (Figure 6). Weekly meetings increased by about 6 % and once or twice by 4 % compared to the results of the first round of the co-creation projects.

In the third period, this positive trend continued. Weekly meetings remained high at 33 %, and the percentage of teams meeting the company representative "once or twice" rose further to 31 %, reflecting growing commitment to regular communication. Despite these improvements, the "Never" category persisted at 11 % in both the first and second periods, and at 13 % for the third period. This suggests that a small portion of students did not participate in any meetings with the company representative, likely due to scheduling

conflicts, team dynamics, or a lack of responsiveness on their part. This highlights an area for potential improvement in future calls, emphasizing the importance of encouraging or facilitating at least minimal engagement between all co-creation teams and company partners.

Figure 6 : Co-creation teams meetings with the company.

2. Companies

Following the submission of solutions, each company was asked to complete a questionnaire about the process, platform, and co-creation teams' solutions. The first period of the INDUSAC call resulted in 10 responses. One of the responses was inadequately completed and therefore excluded from the analysis, yielding 9 valid responses. During the second period of the INDUSAC call, eight questionnaires were received, and all were deemed valid. The third period of the INDUSAC call, 81 companies completed surveys, of which seven surveys were not actively completed and were excluded from analysis.

An example of the company's questionnaire is given in the report's Annex 3.

For the rating, Likert Scale was used to quantitatively assess opinions, attitudes, or behaviours as follows:

Scaling: 1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good.

A total of 23 factors have been identified that are directly associated with the company's assessment of the effectiveness of the INDUSAC project.

- publishing the Challenge
- registration on the platform
- user-friendliness of the use of the platform (user experience of the online platform)
- experience of the offline modules (support material and libraries) of the platform
- communication with the co-creation team
- adequateness of timeline between posting and start of challenge
- adequateness of timeline for solving the Challenge
- revision of applications / Motivation Letters
- assisting the co-creation team in carrying out the project
- preparation of deliverables, reports, etc.
- submission of deliverables, reports, etc.
- punctuality of deliverable submission
- INNOVATIVENESS: How do you estimate the innovative potential of the Solution?
- CREATIVITY: How do you evaluate the creativity of the Solution?
- IMPROVEMENT: How do you evaluate the performance of the Solution compared with your actual/previous solution (if not existent with a competitor's solution)?
- MARKET POTENTIAL: How do you evaluate the market potential of the Solution?
- RELEVANCE: How do you evaluate the relevance of the Solution?
- SOUNDNESS: How do you evaluate the soundness of the work of the co-creation team?
- QUALITY OF WORK: How do you evaluate the quality of the work of the co-creation team?
- SATISFACTION: How satisfied are you with the work of the co-creation team?

2.1. Satisfaction with process and platform

The evaluated companies' satisfaction with the INDUSAC process and platform is presented in Figure 7. In the first period (11.02.2024-29.05.2024) of the INDUSAC call, overall satisfaction with the INDUSAC process and platform was over 70 %. However, the INDUSAC process's lower overall rating was attributed to the lack of a sufficient timeline for addressing the challenge. Companies stated that they would prefer to have set deadlines for submissions to manage their time more effectively. However, this is a Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation Mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations and the challenges should be solvable within 4-8 weeks.

In the second period (30.05.2024-10.10.2024) of the INDUSAC call, satisfaction with the INDUSAC process and platform was over 80 %. The companies' satisfaction with the INDUSAC process and platform significantly improved by at least 10 % for the process and at least 6 % for the platform compared to the first round, as shown in Figure 7.

In the third period (11.10.2024-10.07.2025) of the INDUSAC call, a further increase in satisfaction with the INDUSAC process and platform was observed, as it was over 86% (see Figure 7). The level of satisfaction among the companies regarding the INDUSAC process and platform increased by a minimum of 3% for the process and at least 5% for the platform when compared to the second period.

The aspects most frequently low-evaluated by the companies in the first, second, and third periods are the user-friendliness of the online platform and the support materials and libraries available in the platform's offline modules. Despite these recurring concerns, a steady improvement of over 8% in satisfaction was observed in each period, testifying to the ongoing enhancements of both the INDUSAC process and platform. This upward trend reflects the continuous refinement of the project based on user feedback and its commitment to enhancing the overall co-creation experience.

The top evaluation aspects in all periods were the review of applications and motivation letters, as well as the support provided by the company's representatives.

Figure 7 : Satisfaction with the INDUSAC process and platform for companies.

2.2. Solutions and work of the co-creation team

Figure 8 presents the company's assessment of solutions and the work of the co-creation teams. In the first period of the INDUSAC call, the overall satisfaction with the submitted solution exceeded 77 % for the companies. However, the co-creation teams' solutions were found to be somewhat lacking in innovativeness and creativity, necessitating improvement, and exhibited low market potential, ranging between 65 % and 70 %. Nevertheless, the submitted solutions were regarded as relevant and of satisfactory quality by the companies. In the second period of the INDUSAC call, the overall satisfaction with the submitted solution exceeded 87 % (see Figure 8), which is 10 % more than in the first period. Notable improvements occurred across all areas, with Innovativeness, Creativity, Improvement, and Market Potential increasing significantly, each reaching around 83–88 % compared to the first period. The co-creation teams' solutions were most often deemed to require some improvement compared to existing or competitor solutions, exhibiting low market potential and overall relevance. Despite this, the companies recognised these submitted solutions as innovative, creative, well-structured, and of satisfactory quality.

In the third period of the INDUSAC call, the highest scores were observed across all areas, and the overall satisfaction with the submitted solution exceeded 92 % (see Figure 8), which is 5 % more than the result obtained in the second period. The areas that closed or surpassed the 90 % were Relevance, Soundness, Quality of Work, and Satisfaction. Even categories that initially lagged behind, such as Market Potential and Improvement, achieved strong ratings of approximately 85-86 %.

This consistent period-over-period growth confirms that the INDUSAC project is achieving measurable improvements in both solution quality and participant engagement. The upward trend in all evaluated areas, especially those initially rated lower, shows that the support structure, feedback mechanisms, and experience gained during the co-creation cycles are effectively boosting the performance of participating teams.

Objective 5 “At least 70 % of SMEs reporting that the solution(s) delivered by the co-creation quick intervention were highly relevant to their company and contributed to overcoming the challenge that was identified by them (and which was accepted by the program as being suitable)” can be **confirmed for** all periods of the INDUSAC project's call for students and researchers **since 77 % in 1st period, 87 % in 2nd period and 92 % in 3rd period companies report the overall satisfaction with the solutions.**

Figure 8 : The company's assessment of solutions and work of the co-creation teams.

VI. PROPOSITIONS FOR METHODOLOGY AND PLATFORM IMPROVEMENTS

To ensure the successful development of solutions for the published companies' challenges we addressed some aspects of the methodology in place and the current features of the platform. It was essential to implement some improvements in both the methodology and the platform in order to maximize the effectiveness of the INDUSAC methodology and utilize the platform in further calls.

In the first period (11.02.2024-29.05.2024) of the INDUSAC call, the survey feedback co-creation team members and companies did not reveal any specific issues regarding the methodology used. Some co-creation teams and companies expressed minor dissatisfaction with the platform. Therefore, additional efforts were made to enhance the platform's user-friendliness and to update the support materials and libraries in the offline module to address the observed dissatisfaction.

During the second period (30.05.2024-10.10.2024) of INDUSAC call, the concerns raised in the initial call about specific features of the platform were thoroughly addressed. This proactive approach led to significant improvements, culminating in a remarkable overall satisfaction rate of over 80% from both students and companies involved. The feedback indicated that the adjustments made were well-received, enhancing the overall user experience. Furthermore, the teams involved in co-creating survey feedback and the companies did not have any particular concerns or drawbacks related to the methodology employed in the process.

During the third period of the INDUSAC call (11.10.2024–10.07.2025), the continued refinement of the methodology, process, and platform resulted in remarkably high satisfaction levels—over 90% among co-creation teams and over 85% among companies. These outcomes reflect the success of prior improvements and the adaptability of the INDUSAC approach in responding to earlier feedback.

Building on the enhancements introduced during the second period, the third period demonstrated that the platform's usability, the clarity of methodological guidance, and the overall co-creation experience were significantly strengthened. Notably, neither students nor companies raised any significant concerns regarding the methodology, which testifies to its growing effectiveness and acceptance. The consistently high satisfaction rates across co-creation teams and companies confirm that the INDUSAC framework has matured into a reliable and user-friendly system.

VII. FINAL REMARKS

The INDUSAC projects' call for students and researchers demonstrated success in engaging participants and executing co-creation projects. A **total of 251 challenges** were collected, resulting in the submission of **232 motivation letters**. Of these, **164 were approved**, leading to the **completion of 163 co-creation projects**. These projects involved **318 individual students and researchers**, many of whom participated in multiple co-creation teams. This resulted in **581 instances of student and researcher participation**, each gaining valuable exposure to real business environments throughout the project's lifetime.

The co-creation teams proved to be efficient, with 159 out of 163 submitted solutions being accepted. This indicates the presence of strict yet fair evaluation criteria. The demonstration of skill development among participants emphasizes the positive impact of the project on their professional growth. The extensive feedback obtained through before-and-after-project questionnaires provided valuable insights into the co-creation process. This feedback was important for refining and enhancing the methodology for future cut-offs of the call for students and researchers, ensuring that the initiative remains responsive to participant's needs and continues to evolve. Overall, the call for students and researchers achieved its immediate objectives and established a strong foundation for future iterations. It highlighted participant engagement, skill enhancement, and actionable feedback for ongoing improvement.

VIII. LIST OF REFERENCES

Odić D., Mrgole U., Trobec M. (2025a). FSTP Agreements with Students and Researchers. Deliverable D3.6 in Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centered Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (Horizon Europe project No. 101070297).

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Odić D., Mrgole U., Trobec M. (2025c). Summaries of Implemented Co-Creation Projects with Statistics on the Co-Creation Teams. Deliverable D3.2 in Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centered Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (Horizon Europe project No. 101070297).

IX. TABLE OF CHANGES TO THE PREVIOUS VERSION

page 2	updated History of Changes
page 4	Abstract updated to include reporting on the third period of the co-creation projects.
Page 9	Updated I. TIMELINE OF THE CALL FOR STUDENTS AND RESEARCHERS, by adding a timeline for the 3-9 cut-off dates
page 10	Updated II. NUMBER OF PUBLISHED CHALLENGES, NUMBER OF SUBMITTED MOTIVATION LETTERS, NUMBER OF APPROVED MOTIVATION LETTERS, NUMBER OF FINISHED CO-CREATION PROJECTS by adding results achieved for the third period of INDUSAC call.
page 14	Updated III. LIST OF APPROVED SOLUTIONS to include results of the third period of INDUSAC call.
page 25	Updated IV. LIST OF SUBMITTED BUT NOT APPROVED SOLUTIONS to include Evaluation Board evaluation of solution from the third period of INDUSAC call.
page 28	Updated 1. Students & researchers to include survey results of co-creation teams from the third period of INDUSAC call.
page 30	Updated 1.1. Skills (before & after) to include skill results of co-creation teams from the third period of INDUSAC call. Updated part of the Objective 7 and KPI to include results of all periods of the INDUSAC call.
page 37	Updated 1.2. Satisfaction (before & after) to include skill results of co-creation teams from the third period of INDUSAC call.
page 38	Updated 1.3. Additional feedback to include skill results of co-creation teams from the third period of INDUSAC call.
page 39	Updated 2. Companies to include skill results of co-creation teams from the third period of INDUSAC call.
page 40	Updated 2.1. Satisfaction with process and platform (Companies) to include survey results from the third period of the INDUSAC call.
page 42	Updated 2.2. Solutions and work of the co-creation team to include results from the third period of INDUSAC call Updated Objective 5 to include results of all periods of the INDUSAC call.

page 44	Updated VI. PROPOSITIONS FOR METHODOLOGY AND PLATFORM IMPROVEMENTS to include results from the third period of INDUSAC call.
page 45	Updated VII. FINAL REMARKS to include results of all periods of the INDUSAC call.
page 47	Updated VIII. TABLE OF CHANGES TO THE PREVIOUS VERSION.
page 49	The previous Annex 1, which included summaries of each co-creation team's approved solutions from the first and second periods of the INDUSAC call, was omitted from the report. A complete list of summaries of approved INDUSAC co-creation solutions is available as a separate deliverable, D3.2.
page 61	Updated ANNEX 3 : Questionnaire for Companies after completion of the Co-creation Project

X. ANNEXES

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ANNEX 1 : Template for Evaluation of Solutions

Title of Challenge:

Company:

Co-creation Team:

Criteria (same for INDUSAC Evaluation Board and for companies):

Evaluation criteria	Weighting	Max scoring	Max scoring with weighting	Score	Evaluator
Deliverable quality	30 %	10	3		company
Business performance indicators / Technical performance indicators	60 %	10	6		company
Deadline compliance	10 %	10	1		points given automatically if the Solution is submitted on time
Total	100 %	30	10		

Scoring system with scores 0 to 10 (no decimals).

wherein:

- 0 - no effort made to fulfill any of listed aspects
- 1-2 - some aspects were not covered or all aspects were covered poorly
- 3-4 - all aspects covered but at least half of them poorly
- 5-6 - all aspects covered, some of which are covered poorly while others could be improved
- 7-8 - all aspects clearly presented but could be improved
- 9-10 - all aspects clearly and satisfactorily presented

- Students from co-creation teams with Solutions scoring above the threshold (7 points) will receive payment.

Decision: _____

Justification for the company to describe the deliverable quality (select one option)

- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of excellent and of very high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of acceptable quality.
- Reject the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of very low and unacceptable quality.

ANNEX 2 : Skill Level Survey for Students/Researchers before & after the Project

Questions for co-creation team members upon receiving info about positive selection (before the start of the co-creation project):

Please enter your INDUSAC team ID number:

Enter a personal ID number / code of your choice

(INDUSAC needs this information for comparative analyses only, so do not use your name or any official ID.

You will identify yourself with this number / code again in a second survey after the end of the project.

Recommended form: your initials + your team ID number, eg. JN100001 for John Smith from team #100001)

What is the country of your citizenship or residency?

What is your gender?

I am a

- student → leads to
 - In which country do you study?
 - Choose your area of study
- researcher → leads to
 - What is the name of the public research organisation where you work?
 - Mark your area of research

Please, evaluate your current level of the following soft skills (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - Likert Scale):

- Communication skills
- Negotiation
- Results oriented thinking
- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management

- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership
- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Understanding for international colleagues
- English

Selection (Multiple choice)

- Which skills would you like to develop/improve:
 - o Communication skills
 - o Negotiation
 - o Results oriented thinking
 - o Responsibility
 - o Creativity
 - o Planning skills
 - o Analytical thinking
 - o Critical thinking
 - o Conflict management
 - o Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
 - o Common goal definition
 - o Time management and effective planning
 - o Leadership
 - o Teamwork
 - o Experience in working with companies
 - o Understanding for international colleagues
 - o English

Yes/no questions

Are you familiar with the following methods:

SWOT analysis

Persona Method

Utility analysis

Trend analysis

Scenario analysis

Cost-benefit analyses
Product portfolio analysis / BCG Matrix
White spot analysis
Creating marketing strategies
Value proposition analysis
Developing a business plan
Preparation of business model canvas
Building a Product Service System
Detecting ideas
Empathy map
Kano-method
Building prototypes
Simulation model
Virtual prototype
Target group analysis

Questionnaire for Students/Researchers after Completion of the Co-creation Project

The purpose of the questionnaire is to evaluate the level of upskilling achieved during the co-creation project.

Questions for students/researchers after submission of the final report

Please enter your INDUSAC team ID number:

Name and Surname

Enter a personal ID number / code of your choice

(this is the same ID you identified yourself in the first survey before the project)

What is the country of your citizenship or residency?

What is your gender?

I am a

- student → leads to
 - In which country do you study?
 - Choose your area of study
- researcher → leads to
 - What is the name of the public research organisation where you work?
 - Mark your area of research

Please, evaluate your current level of the following soft skills (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - Likert Scale):

- Communication skills
- Negotiation
- Results oriented thinking
- Responsibility
- Creativity
- Planning skills
- Analytical thinking
- Critical thinking
- Conflict management
- Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
- Common goal definition
- Time management and effective planning
- Leadership

- Teamwork
- Experience in working with companies
- Understanding for international colleagues
- English

Selection (Multiple choice)

- Which skills were significantly developed / improved through the co-creation team project:
 - Communication skills
 - Negotiation
 - Results oriented thinking
 - Responsibility
 - Creativity
 - Planning skills
 - Analytical thinking
 - Critical thinking
 - Conflict management
 - Tolerance and acceptance for different approaches
 - Common goal definition
 - Time management and effective planning
 - Leadership
 - Teamwork
 - Experience in working with companies
 - Understanding for international colleagues
 - English

Yes/no questions

- Are you familiar with the following methods:
 - SWOT analysis
 - Persona Method
 - Utility analysis
 - Trend analysis
 - Scenario analysis
 - Cost-benefit analyses
 - Product portfolio analysis / BCG Matrix

- White spot analysis
- Creating marketing strategies
- Value proposition analysis
- Developing a business plan
- Preparation of business model canvas
- Building a Product Service System
- Detecting ideas
- Empathy map
- Kano-method
- Building prototypes
- Simulation model
- Virtual prototype
- Target group analysis

Please, evaluate your experience in terms of clarity and satisfaction with the process (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - Likert Scale):

Topic	clarity of the process	satisfaction
finding the detailed information about the Challenge		
user-friendliness of the use of the platform (user experience of the online platform)		
method assistance through explanations and templates		
assistance through the proposed process and milestones		

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Topic	clarity of the process	satisfaction
registration on the platform		
creation of a team		
timeline of challenge application process		
timeline for solving the challenge		
submission of application / Motivation Letter		
working in a team - with other students / researchers		
working in a team - with company		
preparation of deliverables (Solution, reports, etc.)		
submission of deliverables (Solution, reports, etc.)		
(students only) financial transaction process		

Any general comments? (text answer) _____

Collaboration

How often did you meet the company representative?

1) Never 2) once or twice 3) bi-weekly 4) weekly 5) more often

Which communication channel did you use?

1) INDUSAC platform 2) Slack 3) WhatsApp or similar Messenger 4) E-Mail 5) Online meeting platform (e.g. teams, zoom) 6) other please specify: _____

How often did you meet with your team members?

1) Never 2) once or twice 3) bi-weekly 4) weekly 5) more often

Which communication channel did you use?

1) INDUSAC platform 2) Slack 3) WhatsApp or similar Messenger 4) E-Mail 5) Online meeting platform (e.g. teams, zoom) 6) other please specify: _____

Did you benefit from working in a multicultural team?

1) Not at all 2) a bit 3) neutral 4) Yes I did 5) Yes a lot

Rate the level of agreement or disagreement with each statement on a scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents "Strongly Disagree" and 5 represents "Strongly Agree."

- The co-creation mechanism encouraged active participation and engagement from all participants.
- The co-creation process encouraged collaboration and co-learning among the participants.
- The co-creation processes incorporated customer research and insights to understand the end-users' needs and preferences.
- The co-creation process fostered interdisciplinary collaboration, integrating perspectives from social sciences and humanities to other disciplines.
- We, as a team, were encouraged to explore ethical considerations and social impact when generating ideas during the co-creation process.
- I was able to participate equally in the decision-making process.
- The co-creation process resulted in solutions that specifically addressed gender-related issues or considerations.
- Overall, the co-creation process successfully prioritised the human aspect (Inclusivity, Gender dimension, Interdisciplinarity, User Perspective, Collaboration, Iterative Feedback, Ethical Considerations) and created a meaningful and inclusive environment.

Any general comments? (text answer) _____

Please, evaluate your current level of agreement with the following statements (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - Likert Scale) + option "I didn't use it":

- Help desk assistance (e.g. value of support received) was adequate.
- It is likely you would recommend participation in such a program to other peers

- Challenges were diverse enough and you were able to find an interesting one fast and start the co-creation process
- The Challenges were well described.
- Companies' expectations were reasonable.
- You are satisfied with the results that your co-creation team submitted,
- You benefited from working in an international environment.

Open questions:

- Appropriateness of funding: did you find funding appropriate, high enough? Were you able to cover all your costs? Considering actual costs and given rational consideration, do you feel that the funding received would be sufficient for supporting more than one co-creation project?
- What is the main reason you applied to INDUSAC open calls (money, connections to students and/or companies/researchers, international experiences, new skills etc.)?
- How would you rate your experience with the provided method recommendations and explanations, templates, process and milestone recommendations?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Would you like the INDUSAC communication team to prepare a success story / a good practice story based on your project and results? If so, the communication team will contact you for more information.

ANNEX 3 : Questionnaire for Companies after completion of the Co-creation Project

Name of your company

Title of your Challenge

Enter the ID of the co-creation team that worked on this Challenge (visible on top of their Motivation Letter)

In the following section (next three questions), please evaluate the co-creation team's Solution.

There are three categories with the following weights:

The company evaluates the deliverable quality of the submitted Solution (30% of the overall score), Business performance indicators and Technical performance indicators (60% of the overall score), Deadline Compliance (10% of the overall score, which is given automatically if the Solution is submitted on time) of the submitted Solution.

Deliverable quality, max 10 points, weight 30 %, amounting to max 3 points

Business / Technical performance indicators, max 10 points, weight 60 %, amounting to max 6 points

Deadline compliance, max 10 points, weight 10 %, amounting to max 1 point

Scoring system for unweighed points:

0 - no effort made to fulfill any of listed aspects

1-2 - some aspects were not covered or all aspects were covered poorly

3-4 - all aspects covered but at least half of them poorly

5-6 - all aspects covered, some of which are covered poorly while others could be improved

7-8 - all aspects clearly presented but could be improved

9-10 - all aspects clearly and satisfactorily presented

Students from co-creation teams with Solutions scoring above the threshold (7 points total) will receive payment.

Please evaluate Deliverable quality, scoring from lowest (0) to highest (3)

Please evaluate Business / Technical performance indicators, scoring from lowest (0) to highest (6)

Please evaluate Deadline compliance, award 1 point for Solution submitted on time

Please select a final decision on the Solution

- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of excellent and of very high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of high quality.
- Approve the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of acceptable quality.
- Reject the Solution: The submitted deliverables are of very low and unacceptable quality.

Questions for company representatives after submission of the final report

Satisfaction with following steps of the whole process (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - **Likert Scale** + option “I didn’t use it”)

- publishing the challenge
- registration on the platform
- user-friendliness of the use of the platform (user experience of the online platform)
- experience of the offline modules (support material and libraries) of the platform
- communication with the co-creation team
- adequateness of timeline between posting and start of challenge
- adequateness of timeline for solving the challenge
- revision of applications / motivation letters
- assisting co-creation team in carrying out the project
- preparation of deliverables, reports, etc.

- submission of deliverables, reports, etc.
- punctuality of deliverable submission

Any general comments? (text answer) _____ 3

Satisfaction with the Solution and work of the co-creation team (1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good - Likert Scale)

- Technical performance indicators:
 - o Innovativeness: How do you estimate the innovative potential of the Solution?
 - o Creativity: How do you evaluate the creativity of the Solution?
 - o Improvement: How do you evaluate the performance of the Solution compared with your actual/previous solution (if not existent with a competitor's solution)?
- Business performance indicators:
 - o Market potential: How do you evaluate the market potential of the Solution?
 - o Relevancy: How do you evaluate the relevance of the Solution?
- Quality
 - o Soundness: How do you evaluate the soundness of the work of the co-creation team?
 - o Quality of work: How do you evaluate the quality of the work of the co-creation team?
 - o Satisfaction: How satisfied are you with the work of the co-creation team?
- Will you use the Solution provided by the co-creation team within your company (No, definitely not – probably not – not decided yet – yes we will – yes, we already started)?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Have all requested deliverables been delivered by the co-creation team?

Tick a box Yes / No:

Would you like the INDUSAC communication team to prepare a success story / a good practice story based on your project and results? If so, the communication team will contact you for more information. 4

Testimonial: please provide a short testimonial, e.g. a letter or written statement of recommendation of something given or done as an expression of esteem, admiration, or gratitude. See two examples below:

“The company that issued the Challenge is active in the services sector. Due to a low number of employees and a busy schedule, it is a Challenge for them to find time to think out-of-the box. Within the INDUSAC co-creation project team, we not only got an opportunity to solve a real-life company problem and provide ideas for improved services but also got experience in international cooperation with fellow students and researchers. We would be happy to participate in similar initiatives in the future!”

“I learned about the INDUSAC at the university where I study. Then I checked the INDUSAC website and there were several Challenges from companies. Three Challenges were really interesting, I joined one co-creation team and we successfully submitted a Motivation Letter. For the first time I was able to be a member of an international co-creation team and worked with a company from France. I was able to contribute my ideas and knowledge. This was really a valuable experience.”

Please provide a short description of the project results - Solution provided by the team (five sentences total). Note that the description will be published on the INDUSAC website and on the EU platform so please don't include confidential information.

On a scale of 1 to 5, how likely is it that you would recommend participation in this type of programme to your peers?

(1 – very poor, 2- poor, 3 – average, 4 – good, 5- very good)

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